

A Study on Customer Awareness, Satisfaction and Investment Behaviour Towards Post Office Savings Schemes with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

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Abstract- Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour. Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour. Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour. Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour.

Keywords: Post Office Savings Schemes, Customer Satisfaction, Investment Behaviour, Savings Patterns, Financial Security, Government-Backed Investments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour.

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Objectives of the Study

- To study customer awareness about post office schemes
- To analyze customer satisfaction
- To examine investment behaviour
- To identify influencing factors
- To provide suggestions

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Post Office Savings Schemes are one of the most trusted investment options in India. These schemes are supported by the Government and provide secure and stable returns. In a developing economy like India, savings play a vital role in ensuring financial stability. People from different income groups prefer these schemes due to their low risk and accessibility. In Coimbatore City, a mix of urban and semi-urban population makes it an ideal place to study customer behaviour.

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III. OVERVIEW OF POST OFFICE SAVINGS SCHEMES

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IV. CUSTOMER AWARENESS

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Customer Satisfaction

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V. INVESTMENT BEHAVIOUR

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Findings

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Suggestions

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VI. CONCLUSION

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